

TETR ARCHs

Transforming Data Reuse in Archaeology

Deliverable 8.5

Storytelling Data User Guide

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Summary

This Deliverable 8.5, titled *Storytelling Data User Guide*, provides an explanation of the Storytelling Data Model, developed as part of the TETRARCHS project. Alongside discussion of the rationale and design principles on which the data model is based, this deliverable includes a full list of its classes and properties, with examples indicating how they should be used. The deliverable closes with guidance on how best to use the data model, with specific advice for both data creators and reusers.

1. Introduction

The storytelling data unit is intended to support the reuse of archaeological data and, more broadly, heritage data for storytelling purposes. It was created within the Transforming Data Reuse in Archaeology (TETRARCHs) project, a three-year European initiative (2022-2025) which aimed to optimise data for reuse by storytellers through bridging knowledge gaps. TETRARCHs achieved this objective by collaborating with several different storytellers, whether archaeological specialists, professionals from memory institutions, or creative practitioners. The storytelling data unit is part of the Sley data model, whose aim is to allow users to weave together archaeological facts with personal and sensory experiences, to craft stories and interpretations which are more just, diverse, and compelling. In weaving, a sley is a tool used to separate and align threads, enabling the formation of patterns. Much like threads in a fabric, the sensory, affective, and cognitive dimensions addressed by the Sley data model are foundational elements of archaeological interpretation and storytelling.

2. Rationale Behind the Storytelling Data Unit

The aim of the storytelling data unit is to facilitate the recording and thus reuse of data for storytelling. As such, it does not focus on the activity of storytelling per se, but rather on filling information gaps. From the different methodologies employed throughout the TETRARCHs project, it was concluded that storytellers have four major areas of interest where data is usually insufficient or difficult to access. Based on the results of Deliverable 3.1, storytellers are reusing in their stories data about people, data relating to the senses, and eliciting particular emotions, as well as the specifics of the places in which these experiences occur. The model focuses on capturing sensory experiences as they are experienced by actors, the emotions and relationships which might be involved in said experiences, as well as the involvement of landscape in these experiences, and their relationship with things and people.

While the model does not focus on narrative structure, as it is not meant to record stories themselves, the usefulness of having narratives accessible as a “data type” has been expressed by different audiences throughout the project. For that reason, this guide also recommends using models such as the [Narrative Ontology](#) or Odeuropa’s [StoryLine Ontology](#). Additional vocabularies can be used by employing the CIDOC CRM property *P2 has type* to reference them.

3. Design Principles and Requirements

The main motivation for the storytelling data model is to maximise reuse for compelling storytelling. As such, it should enable richer forms of data retrieval which have to do with affective and sensory dimensions of the archaeological process. As stated above, four main requirements were underpinning the development of classes in this model, supporting data about:

- emotions, which can serve to inform emotional arcs and provide themes and motifs;
- sensory experiences, supporting immersion, communicating tone and which can be used as narrative triggers;
- people and other-than-human agents, which can in stories become characters;
- and landscapes, providing location, geography, but also non-material dynamics that a story can feed off.

While it was not the intention behind this model to necessarily be an extension of any existing model, for the sake of interoperability, the decision was made to harmonise the model with the logic of CIDOC CRM, as it is (within computational archaeology and digital heritage in the Global North) one of the most ubiquitous data models. Semantic interoperability and integration with other archaeology and heritage data models will hopefully support long term use.

4. Classes

- **E7 Activity:** This ontology employs the CIDOC CRM class E7 Activity, specifically in the sense of a physical action as a process carried out by instances of E39 Actor.
Examples: digging, dancing, walking, fighting.
- **E39 Actor:** This ontology employs the CIDOC CRM class E39 Actor which extends beyond people to other-than-human agents, as we consider other-than-human agents capable of performing intentional actions.
Examples: the archaeologist, the tree, the lake.
- **Y1 Atmosphere:** Derived from Harris & Sørensen's (2010) understanding of atmospheres as an emotional experience which emerges at the intersection of places, things, and people. Atmospheres are the outcome of particular situations, taking place in a particular conceptual place, and the dynamics of different agents.
Examples: dreary, festive, foreboding, peaceful, serene, lively, whimsical, awe-inducing.
- **Y2 Attitude:** An attitude is the result of an actor's beliefs, emotions, and behaviour. An attitude can have a positive, negative, or neutral valence, and can be explicit, meaning conscious, or implicit, meaning unconscious.
Examples: optimistic, confident, cynical, intolerant, curious, detached, indifferent.
- **Y3 Cognitive Process:** This class comprises instances of mental processes related to information acquisition, processing, storing, or recalling, happening within an instance of E39 Actor in relation to a sensory experience.
Examples: thinking, learning, remembering.
- **E3 Condition State:** This ontology employs the CIDOC CRM class E3 Condition State, comprising the states of objects, and extends it to describe the state of conceptual spaces.
Examples: broken, complete, abandoned, in disrepair.
- **Y4 Emotion:** An emotion is understood as the "embodied act of being moved to move", as was coined by Harris & Sørensen (2010). It is the emotion provoked within an actor by a specific instance of L3 Sensory Experience, and which can further trigger other reactions.
Examples: anger, sadness, surprise, awe, fear, embarrassment, pride, hope.

- **Y5 Landscape:** Landscape adopts parts of the definition of Conceptual Space developed by Niccolucci & Felicetti (2025), referring to a place and the fabric of said place, meaning all the material and non-material dynamics which are part of it. This includes social dynamics of the past and present, cultural practices, memories, and discourse. A landscape can be individual or shared, it is not necessarily enduring: it can exist within a person's or group's memory.
Examples: the part of the forest next to the school where the children play, the temple, the Ardennes.

- **Y6 Relational Field:** This class encompasses all types of relationships which can be formed between an instance of E39 Actor and another instance of E39 Actor or an instance of E70 Thing. These relationships are the product of a shared experience (an instance of L3 Sensory Experience) between two instances of E39 Actor, or the relationship an actor can develop with the instance causing the sensory experience.
Examples: attachment, communication, hatred.

- **Y7 Lived Experience:** This class encompasses all events experienced in the life of an instance of E39 Actor, be it a person or group or more-than-human agent. The scale of said events is inconsequential as they are all considered as shaping the identity of the instance of E39 Actor.
Examples: separation from kinship community; end of the Umayyad Caliphate in Spain; disability.

- **L3 Sensory Experience:** This ontology employs the Odeuropa class `od:L3_Sensory_Experience` comprising "activities in which an actor (human or animal) is perceiving a stimulus, namely any action of viewing, smelling, listening, tasting, touching."

- **Y8 State:** State is a sibling class of CIDOC-CRM "E3 Condition State", comprising the states of Actors and other non-human agents (Landscape, Animals) characterised by a certain condition over a time-span. An instance of this class describes a condition that is not necessarily just physical. The nature of that condition can be specified using Y1_Atmosphere or Y2_Attitude, or described using P2 has type.
Examples: tired, abandoned, busy.

- **Y9 Socio-Cultural Context¹:** This class encompasses socio-cultural and ideological contexts associated with an instance of E39 Actor which can be diverse, including specific religious, political, and economic contexts. One instance of E39 Actor can be linked to several different instances of Ideological Context as these can change depending on many factors, including location (geographical), time, and lived experience.
Examples: Sunni Maleki society, Fascist government, colonial context, high social status, low social status, gendered context.

¹ The class Y9 Socio-Cultural Context is about elements which are constitutive of an actor's identity. While we have found that being able to search for information using elements relating to identity is of great interest to different storytellers, creating fixed classes which would define the notion of identity and make it fixed, based on our current notions of what that entails, would be counterproductive. As such, this category of information has been created to attempt to encapsulate what was defined by George Herbert Mead as "a temporal state of self, shaped by past experiences and mediated by memories".

5. Properties

- **y1_sparked (was sparked by)**: This property associates an instance of E2 Temporal Entity that activated/triggered another instance of E2 Temporal Entity. y1_activated has a larger scope than crmsci:O13_Triggered; it identifies an interaction that can occur between various entities. Namely, an L3_Sensory_Experience can spark a Y4_Emotion; a Y6_Relational_Field can be sparked by an (existing) Emotion, or spark a (new) Emotion.
- **y2_had_attitude**: This property associates an instance of E39 Actor (a person, a group, an animal) with an Attitude.
- **y2_had_atmosphere**: This property associates an instance of E70 Actor (a place, a landscape, an object...) with an Atmosphere.
- **y4_involved**: This property explicitly connects an instance of Y4_Emotion with an instance of Y3_Cognitive_Process. Through y4_involved, one can express that an emotion entailed a cognitive process as well.

6. How to Use the Data Model

Data models are made of **entities or classes** (presented in section 4), which represent a concept or a category (e.g., of things, places, emotions, people), and **relationships or properties** (presented in section 5), which represent the way these categories relate to each other.

6.1 For Data Creators

The aim of this data model is to support you in recording a more diverse type of data, which you encounter during your data creation processes. Whether it is while excavating, analysing or any other part of the data creation process, interaction with things and places often leads to a sensory experience which entails emotions, sometimes the creation of relational bonds, and can influence not just thoughts and actions but also archaeological interpretations. Beyond data about objects and facts, these elements (which are an integral part of archaeological workflows and will usually disappear once an excavation's data is archived, sometimes only perceptible in field diaries or the notes of databases) are of utmost importance for storytelling.

Because data which has sensory or emotive dimensions is subjective, providing information about the actor carrying out a sensory experience is necessary to ensure that re-users can understand how, why, and by whom said data was generated. The goal for this data model is not to add fictionalised elements, but to be used to enrich archaeological and heritage datasets, meaning data creators should use it to contextualise their data whenever possible.

Class	Based on
Y1_Atmosphere	Measurable indicators such as light, sound, temporal variation, weather, crowding, and spatial feeling
Y2_Attitude	Related to a person's disposition, whether a historical person, which can be motivated by textual or material evidence, or a contemporary person, which can be based on their statements, tone, or behaviour.
Y3_Cognitive_Process	Can be used to self-report about the data creators' thought processes, or can be inferred from material evidence for a historical person.
Y4_Emotion	Can be used to self-report; emotions can also be assessed through observable indicators. For a historical person, emotions can be expressed in iconography for example.
Y5_Landscape	Describe places beyond their physical boundaries, as places of meaning with intangible dimensions.
Y6_Relational_Field	Can be used to self-report, and relations can also be extrapolated for people of the past based on material evidence (e.g., a worn-out toy shows the child playing with it had an affective relationship with said toy).
Y7_Lived_Experience	Can record everyday practices, routines, or social roles, for an individual or a group. Similarly, based on ethnographic or historical sources.
Y8_State	Can record information regarding temporary conditions of human and non-human actors.
Y9_Socio-Cultural_Context	Can be used to document values, norms, institutions, and other identity markers.

6.2 For Data Reusers

The aim for data reusers is that this data model can support more generous searches in datasets that use it. Each data unit is a fragment of an experience; the goal of this model is for storytellers to be able to access accurate emotive and sensorial data relating to archaeology.

Class	What can it be used for
Y1_Atmosphere	Translate sensory information into narrative cues, it can help foreshadow plot turns, or be a reflection of characters.
Y2_Attitude	Give cues as to what a character's body language might be, how they would speak or interact with other characters, things, or the landscape they are in, and especially what they might notice or ignore because of their attitude.
Y3_Cognitive_Process	Show how decisions are made, and can also in conjunction with E7_Activity inform about the physical movements which might accompany cognitive processes.
Y4_Emotion	Records how a sensory experience moves an actor, in conjunction with other classes it can inform about how a character's actions are motivated, and what specific cognitive processes and relationships an emotion could trigger. This data can also be used to map emotional arcs in a story.
Y5_Landscape	Can be used to shape a character's worldview, as they imply social and cultural dynamics. It can be a way to create constraints, create conflict, or opportunities. Landscapes, especially in conjunction with Y1_Atmosphere, can also be used to illustrate thematic elements of a story.
Y6_Relational_Field	Sheds light on the relationship dynamics which can exist between different agents, whether two people, or a person and the anthropomorphist relationship they might have to a thing. This data can be used to create stakes for characters, and can drive plots.

Y7_Lived_Experience	Can provide information which can be used to establish a character's background, their motivations, perhaps conflicts. It can explain or justify why characters interpret events as they do, why they react to them in specific manners, and why they make the choices they make.
Y8_State	Information regarding states implies specific times and thus transitions, which can be used to drive narration.
Y9_Socio-Cultural_Context	Can provide information which through more research can help understand the socio-cultural dynamics in which people evolved and which might have constrained or helped them.
L3_Sensory_Experience	Can provide information about the sensory reality of actors, such details can be used in many different ways to anchor audiences in a story. Sensory data can be used to ground a scene, to shape tension, and it also ties into an actor's lived experiences as it can trigger their memories or other cognitive processes.

Combining these data categories can facilitate the construction of a narrative. For example, with landscape and atmosphere, the setting of the narrative can be set. Socio-cultural context can be used to define constraints and norms, and lived experience can inform about how a character which was introduced using emotions, cognitive patterns, actions, and attitudes, would behave in this context.

References

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TETRARCHs is making archaeological data accessible to a wider range of people.

The project explores how data from excavations and post-excavation research can be used and reused for educational, creative, and other life-enriching purposes. We work collaboratively across a variety of communities to experiment with storytelling about the past.

For heritage professionals, we create new resources for developing and measuring the effectiveness of archaeological data for storytelling.

For memory institutions like museums and cultural centres, we create reference materials to support you using these new resources for storytelling.

For creatives and local citizens, we will create a platform where you can search for and experiment with storytelling about the past.

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